

Original Research Article

Teaching Mathematics to Children of Immigrant Backgrounds: Primary Teachers' Perspectives from Norway

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ABSTRACT: In this study, we explore primary teachers' perspectives on teaching mathematics to children of immigrant backgrounds in Norway. In doing so, we employ Variation Theory as our theoretical lens, aiming to map and critically explore the variation of perspectives experienced by the teachers. The participants were twelve teachers working in the same school with high numbers of immigrant pupils. A reflexive thematic analysis of individual semi-structured interviews with the teachers reveals insights into language-related challenges of mathematics learning, cultural influences on mathematics learning, strategies employed by teachers for supporting immigrant children in mathematics, and teachers' professional needs. The findings underline the importance of adapting teaching practices to meet the needs of immigrant pupils and a call for further research to enhance educational strategies and teacher education in culturally diverse settings.

KEYWORDS: *mathematics; primary schools; immigrant children; Norway; teachers' perspectives*

In many Western countries, schools have become more explicitly diverse due to immigration (Banks, 2011) and the forced displacement of millions of people (Cooc & Kim, 2023). Regarding perceptions of how cultural and linguistic diversity influences the teaching and learning of various school subjects, mathematics is often allegedly seen as marginally affected by language barriers and as unrelated to culture (Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023; Xenofontos, 2015). Such perceptions, argued in subsequent pages, are far from reality, as linguistic and cultural matters significantly shape mathematics classrooms.

Norwegian society has long been diverse, contrary to beliefs of cultural and ethnic homogeneity widely held in previous decades (Ryymim, 2019). Recent demographic data indicate

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that 21% of the country's population comprises immigrants or people born in Norway to immigrant parents (Statistics Norway, 2024a). Of this percentage, 34% have a refugee background (Statistics Norway, 2024b). Numbers are proportionally larger in schools, with 27% of the pupil population in upper-secondary education in 2022 having immigrant backgrounds (Statistics Norway, 2024c). Despite this, there is still a “tendency to align the term ‘diversity’ with the visible characteristics of ‘foreignness’, for example, the hijab, a non-traditional name or dark skin tone”, while “[t]he term *etnisk norsk* (ethnic Norwegian) is commonly used as a pseudonym for ‘White Norwegian’ in a context in which debate about race and ethnicity is generally discouraged” (Burner & Osler, 2021, p. 3). In addition, many teachers in the country hold negative narratives, specifically concerning newly arrived immigrants forming social relations with Norwegians, acquiring knowledge, and endorsing Norwegian values (Ringrose et al., 2023). Holding onto such narratives may prevent teachers from realising the Norwegian educational vision of adapted education (*tilpasset opplring*), a concept that refers to the creation of adequate learning conditions for all children based on each child's individual needs (Buli-Holmberg & Ekeberg, 2017). The importance of adapted education, inclusion, participation, and communication for all learners are explicitly emphasised in the national curricula of all school subjects, with the mathematics curriculum constituting no exception (Utdanningsdirektoratet, 2020).

A recent study by Green and Iversen (2022) concludes that the increasing number of newly arrived immigrants to Norwegian classrooms impacts native children's performance in mathematics, but not in English and Norwegian, most likely due to the lack of resources for mathematics teaching as opposed to several resources available for language/literacy lessons. Another study from the same context (i.e., Norozi & Ness, 2023) underlines that the successful education of immigrant children presupposes support for teachers' well-being. This, we contend, is critical as many mathematics teachers worldwide sense the interplay between language, culture, and mathematics learning; yet they are uncertain of how to put intuition into action (Apple, 2008; Gutirrez, 2013). Specific to the Norwegian context, despite the stress on the significance of adapted education in policy documents, the concept remains “nebulous”, creating “difficulties realising its practical potential” (Maxwell & Bakke, 2019, p. 101).

The present study seeks answers to the following research question: What perspectives do primary teachers in Norway hold regarding mathematics teaching to children of immigrant backgrounds? We use ‘perspectives’ to encapsulate a blended understanding of teachers' beliefs and professional stories (Xenofontos, 2019). By ‘children of immigrant backgrounds’ (often used in this article interchangeably with ‘immigrant children/pupils’), we refer to individuals who have either moved to Norway, are born to immigrant parents, or are refugees. Exploring our research question is essential for Norway and beyond, as research from different contexts highlights similar concerns about mathematics teachers and teaching (e.g., Anhalt & Rodrguez Prez, 2013; Meeran & van Wyk, 2022; Xenofontos, 2015). At personal and professional levels, this topic holds great significance for both authors. Elias, the first author, is a young teacher who recently began his career at a Norwegian school with a high percentage of immigrant and refugee children. Constantinos, the second author, has similar teaching experiences from his previous work as a teacher in Cyprus. As an academic researcher, he is particularly interested in supporting mathematics learners from marginalised groups. We begin by locating our work in international discussions and developments. Subsequently, we describe the particularities of this study, followed by a presentation and discussion of the main findings. This paper concludes with implications and recommendations for future research.

The Linguistically and Culturally Diverse Mathematics Classroom

There is a common misconception that mathematics as a scientific discipline is universal and independent of culture, and this is prevalent in public discourse and academic circles worldwide (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023). By association, school mathematics is also misconceived as universal, and, as a result of the widespread assumption of its universality, it is examined in international comparative studies (such as TIMSS and PISA)³ more than any other school subject (Jaworski & Phillips, 1999). Nevertheless, as the relevant academic literature informs us, linguistic (e.g., Morgan et al., 2014) and cultural factors (e.g., Andrews, 2007) significantly shape all mathematics classrooms. This reality can become even more complex when pupils in a classroom have diverse immigrant backgrounds (Anhalt & Rodríguez-Pérez, 2013). Below, we briefly discuss these two factors: language and culture.

In all mathematics classrooms, various types of vocabulary can be found (Elbers & de Haan, 2005; Prediger et al., 2022; Slavit & Ernst-Slavit, 2007): vocabulary used in everyday contexts (e.g., clock, orange), in the general academic register (e.g., compare, consecutive), more specialised vocabulary (e.g., angle, number), and, technical mathematical terminology (e.g. acute angle, prime numbers). The interchange between these types can be particularly challenging for other-language learners, especially where words with multiple meanings are involved (e.g., table as furniture item and table as a tool for organising data in statistics). Learning mathematics in a second/foreign language is challenging for many children, not least when mathematical content is presented in verbal contexts, such as word problems (Adetula, 1990; Bernardo, 1999; Kazima, 2008; Setati & Barwell, 2008). Nonetheless, numerous studies from different parts of the world (see Clarkson, 2009; Farrell, 2011; Ní Ríordáin & O'Donoghue, 2009) have come to the same conclusion: Bilingual pupils who possess a high command of both the language of instruction and the language spoken at home tend to perform better in mathematics compared to their monolingual counterparts. While the reasons for this are still underexplored, it is often assumed that, when bilingual children are competent in both languages, they transfer their language-switching flexibility to mathematical thinking, which often involves translations between different types of representations of mathematical ideas (Adu-Gyamfi et al., 2019).

All children are part of different groups, such as their families and local communities, in addition to being part of the mathematics classroom community of practice. In the classroom, children usually interact with classical mathematical knowledge. In addition, as members of other groups, they also gain exposure to various forms of mathematical knowledge beyond the classical, often referred to as funds of knowledge (Williams et al., 2020) or community knowledge (Gutstein, 2016). These other forms of knowledge constitute part of their identities as mathematical learners (Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023). One example can be found in Andrews and Yee (2006), who write about 9-year-old Saqib, a boy of Pakistani origin living with his family in the UK. Saqib enjoys collecting and saving coins found in his father's taxi, which he later donates to charity. This activity holds great significance to Saqib's mathematical identity, as giving to charity is one of the five pillars of Islam that Muslims practice daily. Nevertheless, it is widely documented that teachers around the world do not always welcome into the classroom the mathematical knowledge children bring from home or their communities (see Baker et al., 2003; Crafter & de Abreu, 2010; Gorgorió & de Abreu, 2009; Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023; Stathopoulou & Kalabasis, 2007). In fact, the common rhetoric many teachers appear to reproduce is that of 'this is how we do things here'.

³ TIMSS = Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study [administered by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA)]. PISA = Programme for International Student Assessment [administered by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)].

As mentioned earlier, many teachers have an intuitive understanding of the relationships between language, culture, and mathematics learning. However, they often struggle with implementing this intuition in their teaching practices (Apple, 2008; Gutiérrez, 2013). Despite their good intentions, teachers' practices often contradict research evidence on what is effective in supporting the mathematics learning of pupils from immigrant backgrounds (Adler, 1997; Gorgorio & Planas, 2001; Xenofontos, 2016). Therefore, it is crucial to examine the current practices of teachers within specific educational contexts.

This Study

Variation Theory as a Theoretical Lens Informing Methodology

Our work is rooted in Variation Theory (VT), a theoretical and methodological framework informed by the principles of phenomenography (Marton, 1981). Developed by educational researcher Ference Marton in the early 1980s, phenomenography aimed to document people's experiences and perspectives by exploring the variations in their perceptions of a phenomenon. The core idea of phenomenography is that individuals in a given context perceive and assign meaning to phenomena in diverse ways. Its primary aim was to capture these differing perspectives, revealing misconceptions and highlighting the realities of human experiences (Marton, 1986).

Marton's early work, though foundational, faced criticism for being overly descriptive, focusing on documenting the range of perspectives without offering deeper theoretical insights. In response, Marton refined phenomenography, evolving it into what is now known as Variation Theory (Marton & Booth, 1997). This development clarified that VT is not merely about describing perspectives but also about understanding and interpreting them. In other words, VT emphasises the significance of variation in human experiences and seeks to explain its existence (Orgill, 2012). It has gained attention in mathematics education research (see, for example, Björklund et al., 2021; Melhuish et al., 2020), where researchers have applied VT to investigate how learners grasp mathematical concepts. This body of research focuses on how variations in teaching methods and learning environments influence pupils' understanding, highlighting VT's potential to enhance educational practices by offering insights into effective teaching strategies that accommodate diverse learning needs.

While most studies have concentrated on pupils' perceptions and engagement with mathematical concepts, there is a significant gap in the literature concerning other stakeholders in education. One of the few exceptions is the work of Xenofontos et al. (2024), which examines variation in practices from the perspective of Scottish teachers and their beliefs about equitable teaching. Building on this, the current paper suggests that VT, as a theoretical concept, can be effectively employed to map the diverse perspectives of teachers. Here, we apply VT to explore the varying perspectives of Norwegian primary school teachers regarding their experiences of teaching mathematics to children from immigrant backgrounds. Our study utilises a qualitative research design, gathering data through in-depth interviews with teachers. Through analysis, we identify key patterns in their practices and beliefs. The specific analytical process is outlined later, in the section 'Data collection and analysis'.

Participants

The participants of this study are twelve teachers working at the same primary and lower-secondary school (grunnskole, ages 6–16). It is worth noting that, in Norway, schooling is compulsory throughout this age range, and it is common for many primary and lower-secondary schools to share the same premises. The school was selected because of its high numbers of

immigrant children and the fact that it offers welcome classes⁴ for pupils who do not speak Norwegian, between grades 2–7 (approx. ages 7–12). In agreement with the school administration, participants were contacted directly through the school’s Teams group. The twelve teachers have varied experiences teaching mathematics across compulsory schooling, both in welcome classes and what is known as ordinary classes. To maintain participants’ anonymity, all names in subsequent pages are pseudonyms.

Data Collection and Analysis

All participants were invited to an individually semi-structured interview at their school. The interviews focused on two main aspects: teachers’ perspectives on (a) immigrant pupils and school mathematics, and (b) their own experiences as mathematics teachers of immigrant pupils. The questions were largely inspired by the work of Xenofontos (2015, 2016), who had previously conducted similar research in Cyprus. As the interviews were semi-structured in nature, the questions were neither posed in any particular order nor were they all used with all informants. Table 1 presents some sample questions, to provide readers with more details about the topics covered during the interviews. Each interview was transcribed verbatim soon after it had been conducted.

Dimensions	Sample Questions
Teachers’ perspectives on immigrant pupils and school mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● From your experience, how do children of immigrant backgrounds participate in the mathematics classroom? ● What kinds of challenges and opportunities do these children experience as mathematics learners? ● Can you give any specific examples from your own experience? ● What similarities and/or differences have you observed between immigrant children and children born and raised in Norway? ● To what can these similarities and/or differences be attributed?
Teachers’ perspectives on their own experiences as mathematics teachers of immigrant pupils	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● In what ways does the diversity of the pupil population influence your day-to-day work as a mathematics teacher? ● How do you support immigrant children as mathematics learners? ● Can you give specific examples from your own experience? ● How does the school administration support you as a teacher? ● What kind of support would you like to have so that you can better facilitate mathematics learning for immigrant pupils?

Table 1. *The interview guide—Sample Questions.*

Without the existence of specific recommendations for capturing the variation of perspectives (Marton & Booth, 1997), studies based on VT employ a variety of data analyses approaches (see Björklund et al., 2021; Melhuish et al., 2020). Therefore, we opted for a reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2021), as it can illuminate how perspectives and beliefs are constructed within unique socio-cultural contexts, similar to the approach taken by Xenofontos et al. (2024). Inspired

⁴ Newly arrived immigrant children in primary and lower secondary schools typically spend one or two years in welcome classes, which may be held at their local school or another location, before transitioning to mainstream classes with peers of the same age (Fandrem et al., 2024). These classes vary in classification across different regions of Norway, but they generally share common characteristics, such as being segregated and primarily focused on language learning (Hilt, 2017). Older pupils without a school diploma from their home or transit countries are placed in Adult Education centres managed by the local municipality (Ringrose et al., 2023). Those over the age of 16 are enrolled in specific units within mainstream upper secondary schools, referred to as ‘combination classes’.

by constant comparative analyses techniques (Strauss & Corbin, 1998), aiming not to develop new theories but to support the analysis with a structured, iterative coding process, our analytical process involved open, axial, and selective coding phases, where data were progressively categorised and analysed to form coherent themes. Following Braun and Clarke (2021), our approach involved six phases: familiarising with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and finally, producing a comprehensive report. Each phase was carefully planned to ensure a deep, nuanced understanding of the data, aiming to present findings that are coherent, logical, and resonating with the informants' experiences. The four themes that emerged from this process are discussed in detail in subsequent pages.

Ethical Considerations

This project received ethical approval from the Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD, recently renamed Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research – Sikt). Participants were informed in writing and orally about the purposes of the project, and all signed consent forms for their participation. All measures have been taken to maintain their anonymity. To ensure the rigour and quality of our analysis, we applied the trustworthiness criteria outlined by Lincoln and Guba (1985). For instance, we used investigator triangulation, where the two authors provided insider and outsider perspectives to enhance the credibility of our findings. While we acknowledge that our work is specific to the Norwegian sociocultural context, our methodology can be transferable to other settings to investigate teachers' perspectives on mathematics teaching and learning. We, however, refrain from making universal claims or generalisations about the applicability of our findings in other contexts.

Findings and Discussion

In the following pages, we unpack four themes that emerged from our analyses. In doing so, we make connections between our findings and the relevant literature. The first two themes focus on teachers' perspectives regarding the linguistic and cultural challenges met by immigrant children in mathematics learning. The third theme deals with teachers' self-reported teaching strategies for supporting immigrant children's mathematics learning. Lastly, this theme is concerned with what participants identified as associated professional needs. Readers should keep in mind that, in acknowledging the exploratory nature of our work, framed by a VT point of view, we bring new literature into the discussion of our findings, and do not limit ourselves to the literature introduced in previous pages.

Language-Related Challenges

All teachers in this study commented on the profound language-related challenges experienced by immigrant children in the mathematics classroom. One such challenge concerns the interplay between everyday language and mathematical terminology, as well as the subtle differences between word meanings in different registers (Prediger et al., 2019; Slavit & Ernst-Slavit, 2007; Wolf & Leon, 2009). Amalie, for instance, gave examples of words such as “biggest, smallest, closest, in between, and many others, that are often used in mathematics. I need to repeat them again and again, and explain what they mean in each context”. Emma, in turn, talked about the use of prepositions, how they can change the meaning of a sentence, and how these changes may have an impact on mathematics learning:

Prepositions are difficult; they [immigrant children] mix them up. When they don't understand something they often get stuck and do not move on. Prepositions are very

important in mathematics, but also in all other subjects. [...] In Norwegian, we have so many different prepositions, and the use of each may change the meaning of a sentence. This can be particularly challenging when mathematical ideas are presented verbally.

In addition, all teachers talked about the challenges children face due to “difficult language and too many instructions” (Isabell) in tasks/assignments. This observation is consistent with previous studies that argue how immigrant children who are in the process of learning the language of instruction encounter difficulties related to the linguistic complexity and structure of the mathematical task text (Prediger et al., 2019; Haag et al., 2013), the order in which the information in the task is introduced (Nordlander & Nordlander, 2009), hidden, irrelevant, or redundant information (Reed, 1998), and misleading keywords (Hegarty et al., 1995; Verschaffel et al., 2000). To address these issues in her classroom, Amalie recommended working with simplified language tasks and gradually moving to more complex language and concepts:

Working with text assignments can be challenging. While some children find it easy to memorise multiplication tables and perform calculations, it doesn't necessarily mean they understand what they're doing. To truly learn and develop a mathematical language, it's important to engage in conversations about mathematics and work on problems together. We need to talk and do mathematics together. It's essential to start with simple mathematical concepts, so that children can learn the language associated with them more easily. Once we see that they've developed an understanding, we can move on to more complex concepts and language.

Contrary to Amalie, who starts with easier linguistic tasks, Juliana's approach involves first building up the language skills of her pupils. In her view, by learning everyday concepts, pupils can apply their mathematical knowledge to text tasks more efficiently, as they “then have the language to understand what the task wants.” Such an approach is consistent with Olafsen and Maugesten's (2015) recommendation that mathematics teaching should be based on pupils' language and experiences. It also allows pupils to use familiar everyday language as a starting point in constructing mathematical concepts.

Apart from the linguistic challenges directly impacting mathematics learning, as presented above, several teachers stressed how challenges may also have an indirect impact, through a negative influence on children's socialisation and relationship building. In Emma's words, “[t]hings become more difficult during break time and after school, when children don't have a teacher to support them linguistically. That's when communication problems become bigger”. Sofie shared a similar view, arguing that “it's not just about learning Norwegian. It's also about having friends and being accepted [...] Many immigrant children don't feel comfortable going to the teacher and saying I don't understand; can you help me? What should I do here?” Teachers' comments here are in line with previous studies concluding that social relationships can have a major impact on immigrant children's social relationships and their participation in the mathematics classroom (Civil & Hunter, 2015; Takeuchi et al., 2019).

To us, the language-related challenges in mathematics reported by teachers reflect broader systemic inequities that immigrant pupils face within the education system. The teachers' observations highlight how language barriers can reinforce educational disadvantages, contributing to a cycle of marginalisation (see Barwell, 2018; Ingram et al., 2024). Despite various policy initiatives in Norway aimed at promoting inclusive education, such as language learning in welcome classes, these measures fall short. The lack of targeted language support and culturally responsive teaching practices highlights a significant gap between policy intentions and what actually happens in classrooms.

This disparity underlines the urgent need for systemic reform to ensure that language proficiency is not a gatekeeper – or an excuse, for that matter – for denying access to educational opportunities in mathematics and other subjects. Effective interventions must go beyond the classroom, fostering inclusive environments that promote social cohesion and provide immigrant pupils with equal opportunities to succeed. It is crucial that the education system directly addresses these injustices by implementing robust, equitable measures to dismantle barriers to learning and participation. To achieve this, we must embrace alternative ways of communicating mathematical ideas, such as using pupils' home languages, translanguaging, gestures, drawings, and objects. This shift can help move us away from deficit perspectives that focus solely on children's lack of proficiency in the language of instruction (Dominguez et al., 2023). Only through such a transformative approach can we hope to achieve true educational equity and empower all pupils, regardless of their linguistic or cultural background.

Culture-Related Challenges

A second theme discussed by all teachers concerns pupils' backgrounds and home cultures, and how these relate to their participation in the mathematics classroom. This theme aligns with studies showing that pupils' cultural backgrounds, including language, significantly affect their mathematical learning (Anhalt & Rodríguez-Pérez, 2013; Xenofontos, 2015; Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023; Zevenbergen, 2000). For instance, Mia argued that children with cultural backgrounds closer to Norwegian culture find adjustment easier, similar to the concept of cultural distance used by Gorgorió and Planas (2005). In Mia's own words, “[i]f they [immigrant children] come from European backgrounds, I find that they understand things much faster in mathematics than those who come from non-European countries”. She also commented on how different children's experiences can be based on the content of mathematics curricula in their countries of origin:

Some children may be in the seventh grade here in Norway but have never encountered statistics before because statistics is not part of the curriculum in the countries from which they come. Likewise, many pupils, especially those from Eastern European countries, have already learnt algebra at the junior level, while here we learn it much later. [...] In countries like the UK and the USA, the units used for volume and other measurements are completely different from the rest of the world.

Participants in this study appeared both aware and open to the fact that pupils bring different mathematical experiences from home to the classroom. For example, as Emma argued, “I have several pupils who say mum and dad have taught me a different way of doing it, and I say that's great, go on and use this method, if you prefer”. Nonetheless, she admitted, “I haven't dug too much into the different methods they learn at home because they often can't explain how they do it. But that's perfectly fine with me, as long as we arrive at the same answer”. On the one hand, we consider Emma's comment (also supported by other participants) to be positive. It is not always the case that teachers encourage children to use their home methods in the classroom. In fact, several studies in Norway (e.g., Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023) and elsewhere (e.g., Civil, 2018 in the USA; Crafter & de Abreu, 2010 in the UK; Gorgorió & de Abreu, 2009 in Spain; Stathopoulou & Kalabasis, 2007 in Greece) have concluded that many teachers discourage children from using their home methods in the formal context of the classroom. On the other hand, however, we find comments like those of Emma quite problematic. Home methods, also known as ‘funds of knowledge’ (Williams et al., 2020) or ‘community knowledge’ (Gutstein, 2016), offer opportunities to explore diverse algorithms and their cultural contexts. When teachers merely allow pupils to use home methods in the classroom without further exploration, these opportunities are lost.

It appears that the current educational framework often fails to recognise and integrate the diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds of immigrant pupils, thereby perpetuating systemic inequities. For example, Mia's comment that children from European backgrounds adapt more easily than those from non-European countries reflects a problematic perspective. This viewpoint suggests a perceived superiority of European immigrants, oversimplifying the challenges faced by pupils from other ethnic groups and reinforcing cultural biases (César & Favilli, 2005; Xenofontos, 2015). It fails to acknowledge the valuable mathematical practices that pupils bring from their home cultures. When teachers overlook these practices, they miss opportunities to create a more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment. This not only hinders the academic progress of immigrant children but also marginalises their identities and experiences. It is essential for policymakers and educators to develop strategies that bridge the gap between home and school mathematical practices. By valuing and incorporating pupils' cultural knowledge, the education system can move towards greater equity and social justice.

Teaching Strategies for Supporting Immigrant Children

Teachers' self-reported strategies to support immigrant children's (mathematical) learning can be clustered into two types. The first type concerns general pedagogical strategies that can be applied to various school subjects, not just mathematics. Similar strategies have been documented in previous studies, both in Norway and beyond (e.g., Jordet, 2010; Skaugen & Fiskum, 2015; Waite et al., 2015). Ida, for example, whose main responsibilities were in welcome classes for newly arrived immigrants, talked about body language as a way to help clarify things. In her own words, "I actively use the body; I use gestures a lot and express with my body, with body language what I want to say". Another example comes from Emma (as well as other teachers), who commented on the "use of translation apps, like Google Translate, to communicate with my pupils".

The second type regards mathematics-specific strategies, as the teachers made explicit references to how these strategies support the teaching and learning of the subject. Olivia talked about using songs to accompany mathematical concepts in her teaching as a way to improve children's language skills and vocabulary. As she said, "Each week, we have a new song, which we sing every day. We also use songs about each season, which vary from month to month". In turn, Alex was among the few teachers who argued that "[i]n the welcome classes, I have pupils who are, age-wise, in grades 5–7. I give them mathematical tasks that are for grade 4. I want to be sure that they can master these tasks before we move on to more age-appropriate ones. I also avoid giving them tasks that have extensive text". Amalie admitted doing the same, as "I need to make sure that basic mathematical concepts are in place before children can move on to more advanced ones". This strategy appears to be common in other contexts as well (e.g., Xenofontos, 2016). However, we see this as a strategy that places pupils in an inferior position (Bartell et al., 2017; Moschkovich, 2013), having negative consequences, as it slows down children's progression since the tasks are not adapted to the cognitive level of pupils (Olafsen & Maugesten, 2015).

Eleven out of twelve teachers emphasised the importance of using visual support, like pictures/images and concrete materials, to represent mathematical concepts. As Mia said, "I often use images of pizza to explain fractions". To stress the importance of visualisation, Isabel talked about a glossary she created with her pupils. This strategy is also reported by teachers working with immigrant pupils in other countries (e.g., Xenofontos, 2016). As she said:

In my classroom, I use lots of visual aids. [...] Visualising bridges the gap between what pupils can and can't do. And yes, I strongly believe that it is important for teachers to have good materials to use. [...] One example is a glossary. We add concepts in Norwegian, then a picture of each concept, and then search for the concept in the native language of each pupil.

Overall, all 12 teachers in our study drew attention to the importance of differentiating their teaching to address the needs of their immigrant pupils. This is, perhaps, unsurprising, especially when the concept of adapted education holds a central role in Norwegian educational discourse (Buli-Holmberg & Ekeberg, 2017). Yet, as the concept continues to be used vaguely in policy documents (Maxwell & Bakke, 2019), we note that our participants talked about their own interpretations of how differentiation can take place to support their immigrant pupils. While some of the self-reported strategies are supported by research evidence (e.g., the importance of visualisation, embodied learning, the use of translation apps), other strategies, as research suggests, may have a negative impact on children's learning (e.g., Alex's statement of giving pupils tasks of lower cognitive demands that do not correspond to their age, merely because the vocabulary is simpler).

The strategies employed by teachers, as reported above, highlight a critical sociopolitical issue within the educational system. While well-meaning, some of these strategies may inadvertently reinforce inequalities by positioning immigrant pupils as inherently deficient, thus justifying a lower academic expectation (Civil, 2018; Xenofontos, 2015). Such approaches can perpetuate a cycle of underachievement and limit the educational and social potential of these pupils. Moreover, the reliance on differentiation without a robust and nuanced understanding of the cultural and cognitive needs of immigrant pupils risks entrenching stereotypes and biases within the classroom. To foster genuine equity, educational policies and practices must go beyond superficial adaptations and address the structural barriers that immigrant children face. This requires a comprehensive approach that includes culturally responsive pedagogy, ongoing teacher professional development in multicultural competence, and systemic support for integrating diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds into the curriculum (Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023). By adopting such measures, the education system can better support immigrant pupils, ensuring they receive an education that is both inclusive and equitable, ultimately challenging the power structures that maintain social inequalities and fostering a more just and cohesive society.

Teachers' Professional Needs

All teachers emphasised professional needs and support they wish they had to aid immigrant children's learning, particularly in mathematics. While their responses varied from person to person, significant overlaps are observed and discussed here. Several participants pointed out that their teacher education studies did not include topics on linguistic and cultural diversity, along the lines of what other similar studies concluded in different contexts (see, for example, Chval et al., 2008; Xenofontos, 2016). As Amalie stated, "I can't remember learning anything about minority pupils when I was in teacher education, but this was some years ago. I don't know if things have changed now". Unfortunately, according to Benediktsson (2022), Norwegian teacher education continues to address related issues in quite superficial manners. This is evident from our study, where participants felt inadequately prepared to teach mathematics to minority language pupils. They attributed their sense of readiness to practical experience rather than formal education. For this reason, Sofie pointed out that collaborations and partnerships between teachers from different schools would be helpful in exchanging experiences and ideas. In her own words, "[i]t would be great if we could meet with other teachers from other schools and other welcome classes and share experiences. We don't do this in my school". These insights emphasise the necessity for teacher education programmes to integrate comprehensive, practical components that address the challenges of teaching in diverse classrooms, ensuring that in-service and future teachers are better equipped to meet the needs of all children.

Few teachers commented on the lack of age-appropriate resources for mathematics teaching. This echoes Green and Iversen's (2022) observation that while there are plenty of resources

available for teaching Norwegian and English to non-native children in Norway, there is a dearth of resources for teaching them mathematics. In our study, Tony, for instance, commented on the difficulties he encounters in finding age-appropriate word problems in mathematics for children who are in the process of learning Norwegian:

I teach in welcome classes for grades 5–7. One thing we don't have is word problems appropriate for the ages of these children. Children are 10, 11, 12 years old, but the problems we have are so simple, they are often intended for six, seven, maybe eight-year-olds. [...] If we want to capture the interest and curiosity of children on the subject, we need to provide them with age-appropriate resources.

Effective school-home collaboration can play a central role in the education of other-language learners (Danbolt & Hugo, 2012; Takeuchi et al., 2019). All participants pointed this out in our study. Nevertheless, some teachers in our study commented on how challenging communication with parents can be, especially when many of them do not speak Norwegian. As Leah argued,

[i]t's challenging when parents don't speak Norwegian, or speak very little Norwegian, and on top of that, they don't speak English at all. Then things become difficult. [...] Also, there are some parents who haven't attended school themselves, right? They may be illiterate, feel insecure, and are too shy to come and talk to us.

In such cases, according to Juliana, “quite often, children speak more Norwegian than their parents. [...] I don't think it's fair for children to be responsible to teach their parents Norwegian”. For this reason, Sofie said, “[w]e need more interpreters and teachers who speak the home language of those parents. This is essential for achieving good cooperation between school and home”. For Mia, “[it] is a shame that not all pupils are offered the opportunity to have a bilingual teacher who speaks their home language”.

As teachers' responses indicate, there is a pressing need for a shift in teacher education programmes to better address linguistic and cultural diversity. The lack of comprehensive preparation in these areas places undue pressure on teachers and reflects broader systemic issues within educational policy. This gap perpetuates educational inequity, disproportionately affecting immigrant children. Policymakers must recognise and address this disparity by advocating for reforms that prioritise cultural competence and inclusive pedagogies. The scarcity of age-appropriate mathematical resources for immigrant pupils further marginalises these learners. Effective school-home collaboration, hindered by language barriers and a lack of support structures, demands immediate attention. The call for more interpreters and bilingual teachers is not just a logistical necessity but a sociopolitical imperative that supports immigrant families' rights to participate in their children's education. Our study calls for a concerted effort to reframe educational practices and policies to embrace and support the multicultural fabric of our society.

Conclusions

In this concluding section, we discuss the implications of our research, highlighting its importance and potential impact. We also recognise the limitations of our study and suggest avenues for future research to enhance and expand upon our work.

Implications

Our work has theoretical, methodological, and pedagogical implications. Theoretically, we did not use a specific predetermined theoretical frame through which teachers' perspectives were investigated. Instead, the exploratory nature of our work resembles a grounded-theory approach (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). While we do not claim that this study fully aligns with grounded theory,

as it does not conclude with a proposed theoretical framework, it is important to emphasise that teachers' perspectives on teaching mathematics to immigrant children in Norway share common dimensions documented in other contexts, such as Cyprus (Xenofontos, 2015; 2016). These dimensions include perspectives on language, culture, teaching strategies, and professional needs, indicating that certain core issues transcend specific national contexts.

Methodologically, our work is grounded in Variation Theory (VT), enabling us to study and comprehend the variation of perspectives on a phenomenon held by specific groups in particular contexts (Marton & Booth, 1997). Historically, VT has primarily been used to explore learners' perspectives. Few studies, such as Xenofontos et al. (2024), have employed VT to investigate teachers' perspectives on equitable teaching practices. As explained earlier, in our work here, VT served as the theoretical lens informing our reflexive thematic analysis. Our study contributes to this emerging body of literature by using VT from the teachers' point of view, highlighting how variations in teachers' experiences and beliefs shape their practices and their ability to address diverse pupil needs.

Pedagogically, our study highlights the critical role of teacher education in preparing educators to teach in linguistically and culturally diverse classrooms. The findings indicate that current teacher education programmes in Norway do not adequately address issues related to linguistic and cultural diversity, echoing conclusions from similar studies in other contexts (Chval et al., 2008; Xenofontos, 2016). It is essential for mathematics teacher education programmes to foreground discussions on cultural, social, and political issues and to equip teachers with both theoretical knowledge and practical strategies for responding to diversity in the classroom (Appelbaum, 2023; Civil & Hunter, 2019; Myers et al., 2023; Nolan & Xenofontos, 2023)

Our findings also suggest the need for improved resources and support for teachers working with immigrant pupils. This includes the development of age-appropriate mathematical resources that consider the linguistic capabilities of immigrant pupils, as well as the provision of professional development opportunities focused on multicultural competence. Effective school-home collaboration is another critical area, with language barriers often hindering communication between teachers and parents. The availability of interpreters and bilingual teachers could greatly enhance this collaboration, ensuring that parents are actively involved in their children's education.

Policymakers and educational leaders must recognise and address these disparities by advocating for reforms that prioritise inclusive pedagogies and cultural competence. By adopting a comprehensive approach that integrates diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds into the curriculum, the education system can better support immigrant pupils, ensuring they receive an equitable and high-quality education. This is essential for dismantling structural barriers, challenging existing power dynamics, and fostering a more just and cohesive society where all pupils can thrive academically and personally.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

The study reported here is exploratory in nature, which places it beyond the scope of our work to make generalisations of any kind. Additionally, we have not examined whether teachers from ordinary classes hold similar perspectives to those who teach in welcome classes. This is an important issue that needs further investigation. Our work has a significant limitation as it only relies on interviews, and, as such, classroom experiences are only explored through teachers' narratives. For future research, it is important to include classroom observations to compare what teachers report they do with what they actually do. Finally, it is crucial for further studies, both in Norway and in other contexts, to consider the experiences and perspectives of immigrant (Khilji & Xenofontos, 2023) and non-immigrant pupils (Planas, 2007) in the diverse mathematics classroom.

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